

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Supratman****FIRST NAME: Evlyne****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit, delete text to show actual information below**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

QUIZ: A SUMMARY OF ASSESSMENT

- 1. In order to avoid plagiarism, we have to properly cite the author or source that has provided the information we are using. However, certainly, we can not cite everything. So, when do we not need to cite the source?**
 - When writing ideas and information from other people's work but using our own words.
 - When the information we are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas.¹**
 - When presenting ideas and information by changing a few words and rearranging the sentence structure of the original source.
 - When paraphrasing using a different writing style from the original author.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd edition. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 10.

2. Style guide can encompass many different aspects, except?

- Preferred sentence lengths.
- Voice preferences (active v passive).
- Preferred source of information.²**
- Accepted terminology.

3. Editing and proofreading help turn your revised writing into a clear, stylistic, and accurate copy. One of the editing and proofreading steps is checking for word choice. Which one of the following that is not a problem when we check for word choice?

- Using too many verbs like is, are, was, and were.
- Repetition of the same word.
- Using too many vague words.
- Using first-person pronouns.³**

4. The Turabian style has a general rule for presenting numbers. However, there are situations in which we might modify this rule. Which of the following is a situation and the modification of the general rule?

- Spell out the numbers beginning a sentence.⁴**

² EUCLID 2019, 24–25.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th edition (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 80.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 189.

- Use hyphens for the number that has two words.
- Spell out round numbers followed by hundred, thousand, hundred thousand, million, etc.
- Use arabic numerals for numbers that are part of physical quantities (distances, lengths, temperatures, etc.).

5. Graphic, chart, and table are often used to communicate data visually. Furthermore, based on the Turabian manual, the graphic, chart, and table are expected to reflect some judgments. Which of the following is not the expected judgment?

- As simple as its content allows.
- Provide honest and accurate relevant data.
- Clear and focused.
- Using an attractive intricate design.**⁵

6. At the end of our paper, we are supposed to list all the sources we used in the research and writing process. What do we call for a list of resources that we have used to help us write our assignments but not cited?

- In-text citations.
- Bibliography.**⁶
- Reference list.
- Endnote.

⁵ Turabian, 56,58,63.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd edition. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 59.

7. According to the general rule of the Oxford Style Guide, if there are multiple (correct) ways of doing something, choose the one which uses the least space and the least ink. Which one of the following that is not the example that reflects the general rule?

- Close up spaces and do not use full stops in abbreviations.
- Use lower case wherever possible.
- Spell out ‘and,’ but used ampersands for official titles or names.**⁷
- Only write out numbers up to ten and use figures for 11 onwards.

8. According to the Bluebook, generally, a legal citation is composed of three principal elements. Which of the following is not included in three principal elements of a citation?

- A signal.
- The source of authority.
- Parenthetical information.
- Abbreviation.**⁸

9. The Bluebook mandates the use of introductory signals to sends a shorthand message to the reader about the relationship between the proposition stated and the source or authority cited in relation to that proposition. In the case we want to cite authority that clearly supports a proposition contrary to the main proposition, what introductory signals should we use?

- Contra.

⁷ EUCLID 2020, 74.

⁸ Columbia Law Review et al., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19th edition (Massachusetts: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2010), 3.

- But see.**⁹
- But cf.
- Accord.

10. Abbreviations, as part of rule 6 in the Bluebook, is regularly used in legal citation. Which of the following is the correct provision of abbreviations according to the Bluebook?

- Do not close up all adjacent single capitals.
- Do not close up single capitals with longer abbreviations.**¹⁰
- Every abbreviation should not be followed by a period, except those in which the last letter of the original word is set off from the rest of the abbreviation by an apostrophe.
- Individual numbers, including both numerals and ordinals, are treated as longer abbreviations.

⁹ Bluebook, 55.

¹⁰ Bluebook, 80.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.